

**INFERTILITY: PATRIARCHAL TENDENCIES,
MANIFESTATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS IN AYOBAMI
ADEBAYO'S *STAY WITH ME***

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Abstract

Infertility resonates within social, medical, religious, and economic spheres. The phenomenon is conceived as the inability to achieve a clinical pregnancy after twelve months of unprotected sexual intercourse. Patriarchal and masculine constructions inherent in Africa enforce the preeminence of the male over the female gender, and are evident in reproductive health matters. Empirical reviews depict that usually there is maximum attention on women in issues of infertility in marriage. Therefore, this study fills the lacuna by investigating the infertile male's tendencies, manifestations, and implications in Ayobami Adebayo's *Stay with Me*. Relying on the masculinity and feminist literary theories, it highlights the influence of patriarchy on infertility and draws attention to instances of female oppression in issues of infertility, respectively. Findings show several patriarchal tendencies, such as deceit, silence, evil scheming, indifference, and manipulation, portrayed through Akin. This experience results in emotional and psychological oppression, dysfunctional marriage, and separation. The study concludes that men symbolised by Akin have implicit tendencies that manifest in issues of male infertility with devastating consequences. These are usually fuelled by African cultures and norms, which are equally instruments of enforcing patriarchal and masculine ideologies. Additionally, despite supposed global gains and progress in tackling forms of inequality, abuse, discrimination, and violence against women, glaring expressions and cases of patriarchy persist in Africa even beyond traditional settings.

Keywords: Female Infertility, Implications, Patriarchy, Manifestations, Tendencies

Introduction

Infertility resonates within social, medical, religious, and economic spheres of human society. The phenomenon, according to the World Health Organisation, is the inability to achieve a clinical pregnancy after twelve months of unprotected sexual intercourse. Additionally, Sule et al. opine that infertility involves "the inability to carry a pregnancy

to the delivery of a live baby” (226). Dambo et al. aver that infertility encompasses the inability to carry a pregnancy to full term (1653). It can be voluntary or involuntary (Ngwu 1). Infertility affects 60 – 80 million couples annually around the world (Deyhoul et al. 24). Therefore, infertility is a global health problem that requires serious attention.

According to Gijssels and Magalla, cited in Ali et al., infertility is attributed to evil forces in Tanzania (2). The authors further claim that in Pakistan, the prevalent belief about the cause of infertility is supernatural, such as black magic and jinn (5). Dimka and Dein’s ethnographic research on perceptions of infertility in the Plateau region of Nigeria attributed it to evil forces and spirits. In the world of the spirits, a woman’s womb can be tied, blocked, or inverted (108). Drawing from this, the scholars reiterate that spirits are contributory factors to infertility on the Nigerian plateau. Moreover, psychological factors inhibiting fertility in females include fear of motherhood, fear of death during childbirth, and fear of having a bad body shape after delivery (Dambo et al. 1655).

In Sub-Saharan African countries, children are considered priceless. Mburugu and Adams, cited in Odek et al., corroborate the importance attached to procreation in African marriages (2). Roupa et al. contend that procreation completes a woman’s life. In Ghana, West Africa, infertile women are tagged and derided. A childless woman in the Akan ethnic group is known as ‘Oboninoor Osaadwee’, while among the Gas and Adangbes she is termed ‘kene’; this word has no literal meaning but denotes barrenness. These tags, however, refer to emptiness and worthlessness (Donkor 27). In Nigeria, the absence of children in a marriage results in divorce and abandonment (Dambo et al. 1655). Similarly, Nwosu and Onwe submit that infertility is perceived as a woman’s shortcoming in Nigeria. (41) and infertile women are regarded as evil beings and excluded from social activities. In a similar vein, among the Yoruba in the South Western part of Nigeria, children are indispensable in marriage, and the more the children, the greater the prestige. (Olusola and Ojo 79). The Yoruba oral literature equally reflects these beliefs (Olusola and Ojo 79). Additionally, infertile women in this ethnic group are addressed with the tag ‘agon’, which is derived from the verb “gon”, which means to despise (Pearce73).

These ill treatments meted out to women, especially in Africa, regarding reproductive health matters, raise concerns over the plight of women. In contrast, several researchers have articulated views that are at variance with the position enumerated above. Baylis avers that infertility is a disease of two persons, not just a woman’s problem (713). Sathyaraj and Chinmay describe infertility as “a gender neutral health predicament” (609). From the foregoing, it is clear that issues of infertility focus more on women than men. Women are constant recipients of insults and abuse following infertility or childlessness. Therefore, the need to investigate

the situation when a man is responsible for such, specifically the tendencies, manifestations, and implications of infertility in a man's life.

Empirical Review of *Stay with Me*

Gbadegesin applies corpus linguistics and critical discourse analysis to examine the use of the pronoun 'I' and its Ngram realizations to show the male character's personal struggles with infertility in Ayobami's *Stay with Me*, as the author is sympathetic to Akin's plight. Abianji - Menang supports and stands with women who are mostly blamed for infertility (271). However, Gbadegesin affirms that an erect penis is imperative for the positive self - definition as well as self -actualization of a male in the Nigerian context (1). Fwangyil corroborates that male virility has an impact on men's personality.

Moreover, Yeboah et al. note that infertility is maximally examined in literary texts but scarcely discussed in African society (169). Similarly, Abianji - Menang concedes that male infertility is a rare discourse (Abianji- Menang 277). On the part of Abianji - Menang, she submits that there is the existence of both male and female infertility, thus, it jettisons the feminization of infertility (281). Further, she affirms that Adebayo, through her work, sensitizes and condemns superstitious beliefs in Africa concerning reproductive health conditions and sickle cell anaemia (Abianji- Menang 273, 281). In this same vein, Yeboah et al. direct the attention of society to 'silent matters' regarding infertility (174). The scholars submit that Yejide, through her utterances, accepts the blame for their childlessness (174). Similarly, Abianji- Menang contends that child birthing is believed to be solely the responsibility of women as a cultural role (274).

The above reviews depict that the focus on infertility is usually on the women, with little attention directed at the men. Specifically, this study fills the lacuna by investigating patriarchal tendencies, manifestations, and implications in infertility as explored in Ayobami Adebayo's *Stay with Me*.

Theoretical Framework

This discourse is hinged on masculinity and feminist literary theories. According to Adegbite, masculinity refers to behavioural roles which men are expected to perform (134). Masculinity is socially and culturally constructed; this necessitates that societies or cultures stipulate the standards of masculinity. Hence, its meaning and manifestations differ in societies. Masculinity describes men as well as the functions they perform in a given society. Similarly,

Masculinity is a cluster of norms, values, and behavioural patterns expressing implicit as well as explicit expectations of how men should act and represent themselves to others. Ideologies of

masculinity like those of femininity are culturally and historically constructed, their meanings continually contested and always in the process of being renegotiated in the context of existing power relations (Jegade 109).

Cornell notes that masculinity is ‘the pattern or configuration of social practices linked to the position of men in the gender order, and socially distinguished from practices linked to the position of women’ (40). Moreover, Haywood, cited by Jegede, submits that masculinism is an ideology that affirms the innate superior stance of males and further vindicates the oppression and domination of females. In sum, masculinism foregrounds the superiority of males while relegating females to the background (Jegade 109). Correspondingly, feminist theories present masculinity as ideologically oriented and as such a set of rules imposed on women by men to exert dominance and control over them. Masculinity differs from place to place, and its construction is therefore impacted by different cultures and different historical periods (Cornell 43).

However, there is the possibility of multiple definitions of masculinities, albeit specific relationships exist between diverse forms of masculinity (Cornell 43). Significantly, some masculinities are revered while some are spited. Similarly, some are discriminated against, and some are esteemed due to their outstanding attributes. Moreover, Jegede opines that universally, there are conventional avenues of attaining masculinity, such as fatherhood, sports, and career (110). Summarily, masculinity on one hand implies behaviours, roles, norms, and values men are expected to perform, and masculinism on the other hand refers to an ideology that projects the superiority of males and supports the oppression of women. In addition, masculinism as an ideology is at variance with feminism.

Feminist literary theory arose in the 1960s and has its roots in the feminist movements of the 19th century. Its tenets are contained in the publication, *A Vindication of the Rights of Woman*, by Mary Wollstonecraft. The theory disapproves of callous treatments meted out on women and scrutinizes literary works for cracks in masculine imaginaries, on how it has reduced women to a state of silence (Childs and Fowler 87). More so, feminist criticism interrogates imaginaries that present women as the ‘other’ as well as ‘second- class citizens’ (Nolas-Alausa 165). Moreover, feminism aims to identify and expose the diverse oppressions of women by men. It seeks to uncover the oppression and domination of women as depicted in literary texts. It aims to liberate women from the domination of patriarchy and empower women to withstand subjugation from oppressive patriarchal traditions. According to Sotunsa:

Feminist literary criticism confronts patriarchal values. It attempts to unveil the prejudices embedded in the appreciation of arts and cultural artifacts. It also exposes how the linguistic medium promotes and transmits the values of male domination. Feminism's major aim is to combat female oppression and repression in all forms (8).

Feminist literary theory deconstructs false male perspectives against women. It further reconstructs the image of women as well as rescues them from hostile patriarchal practices, which have relegated them to the background. Feminist ideology refutes the balanced attention previously apportioned to male issues and interests; instead, it undertakes to explore female issues, concerns, and thoughts (Nolas-Alausa 165). Accordingly, feminism aims to refine, refurbish, and redefine the status of women in different spheres of human endeavours.

Patriarchal Tendencies and Manifestations in Infertility

The various patriarchal tendencies and manifestations in infertility are examined in *Stay with Me*, which include:

Deceit/Silence

The couple, Yejide and Akin, are unable to conceive, which prompts medical tests that confirm Yejide is healthy. Akin hides behind a veil of deceit and tells the doctor that their sex life is good, while he has issues with his erection. To prevent Yejide from speaking to the doctor, he holds her hand when the doctor asks about their sex life, preventing her from making any comment. This action is subtle and implicit, yet it carries weight, as it weakens her resolve to reveal their sexual difficulty. Akin has a subtle tendency to conceal what will hurt him. Before this time, Yejide notices something strange during coitus. Nevertheless, Akin has previously been diagnosed with erectile dysfunction. He discovers he has a challenge as a student at the University of Lagos. Akin says:

It was during that year that I told him I'd never had an erection. At first, he laughed, but realising I was serious, he scratched the back of his head and told me not to worry because it would happen when I met the right girl (279).

Consequently, he visits the Lagos State University Teaching Hospital for a medical appointment with a urologist. Such visits are concealed and presented to his wife as attending official meetings. According to Uadia and Emokpae, erectile dysfunction constitutes a factor for infertility, which is among the male factors that inhibit fertility (49). Markedly, Akin's culture upholds the perspective of a perfect man, and

obviously, one devoid of reproductive health challenges. Therefore, this notion births a tendency in Akin such that he keeps silent to the doctor about his weird sexual life to the doctor. Similarly, this masculine notion clouds him from disclosing or confiding in his wife, Yejide, about his erectile dysfunction diagnosis. In a vein similar to this, masculinity spells out the acceptable behaviour for a man. Hence, Akin manifests this as he remains mute to the incessant delegations about their childlessness. He fails to speak out that he is the reason for Yejide's assumed infertility. Gbadegesin explains that "Men's experience of shame is therefore, often masked with restrictive emotionality, pretense and sometimes aggression which are also considered masculine characteristics" (2).

Evil Scheming

Further, Akin's tendency to silence in the face of urgent and serious matter as infertility, manifests in his evil scheming on how to impregnate Yejide (63). Apparently, his silence is symbolic of his evil plans and schemes. However, masculinity demands that men assert themselves through various means to show their manliness. This expectation further fuels his actions; assuming he opened up to his family, a better solution would have been sought. Moreover, the societal expectations that he become a father equally mount pressure on him to proffer a solution to their childlessness. Akin, in a bid not to be tagged a failure, convinces his brother, Dotun, to assist in impregnating his wife. Consequently, Akin's decision is fueled by the standards and notions of his society on what makes a man. He gives a clue to his evil scheme, of going to Lagos to plead with his brother, Dotun, to impregnate Yejide. Patriarchal tendencies are shown by Akin as he schemes to lure Yejide to sleep with Dotun.

Again, masculinism as an ideology that enhances the superiority of males while proffering reasons for the oppression of females, subtly manifests in the character of Akin. This further drives his evil plan to have Yejide impregnated by his brother, without recourse to the consequences. Similarly, Akin's emotional oppression of his wife through spiteful words is propelled by the masculine superiority notion. Significantly, he utilizes the weapon of blackmail to facilitate his plans. Upon the arrival of Dotun to carry out the deal, Akin, unknown to Yejide, picks a quarrel with her. Akin goes further to lash out at Yejide, which is a tactic to lure his brother and make him see reasons to carry out the deal of impregnating her. Akin rants:

You have been sent away from antenatal classes, Yejide. You had five scans, five different doctors, in Ilesa, Ife, and Ibadan, you are not pregnant, you are delusional! ... Yejide, this has to stop. Please, I beg you. Dotun, please talk to her. I have talked, and

talked, my mouth is starting to peel off because of all the talking (115).

This accurate portrayal of the evil inclinations of patriarchy corroborates the belief that patriarchy and masculinity are often perpetrators of subjugation. Akin emotionally oppresses his wife through false and harsh accusations, which results in wounding her emotions and hence making her an easy prey for Dotun. He hides his medical diagnosis from his wife and devises another means to solve the problem, which places his wife in jeopardy. This also accentuates the fact that patriarchy is sometimes selfish, and men embark on endeavours that will only benefit themselves, with little or no recourse to their wives' feelings. Conversely, feminism seeks to castigate and combat every form of subjugation against women. These masculine and patriarchal manifestations, which Akin exhibits, are condemned by feminism.

Indifference

Additionally, Akin portrays indifference as a tendency. He openly insults Yejide, notwithstanding that he is responsible for her assumed infertility. Akin reveals his wife's mental condition - pseudocyesis to Dotun. Akin shamelessly tells his brother: "She has a condition, she's seeing a doctor" (115). Therefore, Akin's ego and desire to conform to the conventions of his society push him to do something immoral to solve his problem. Consequently, Akin betrays Yejide, despite their marriage bond, which has lasted for many years. Furthermore, Masculinity explicates ways of becoming a man in a definite culture; this is explicitly demonstrated by Akin's efforts as well as those of his family. Evidently, fatherhood is one of the ways of becoming a man in this African society. Little wonder, the fights against Yejide for failing to contribute to having her husband attain this status. This novel is in parallel with Lola Shoneyin's *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives*, where Baba Segi equally confronts his wife, Bolanle, for failing to become pregnant, thereby depriving him of fathering her children. In a vein similar to this, this society upholds fatherhood as a value. Akin, being fully aware of this, makes it his priority without considering the route. Akin is expected by his society to comply and take action to father a child. Therefore, without a child from his marriage, the society reacts by sending a delegation led by Baba Lola, Akin's uncle, to coerce him into marrying another wife. Significantly, his non-compliance is met with resistance and eventual enforcement of a second wife.

Lopsided Practices

In Africa, patriarchy entails that men are deified and revered. Consequently, Funmi, asking Akin how Yejide becomes pregnant, since his penis does not achieve the required erection, is an abomination. A man's impotency is never voiced out because it is a way of emasculating him. On the other hand, it is normal to talk about a barren woman. This shows an unbalanced equation inherent in patriarchal societies such as

Africa. Akin reacts to Funmi against the unconventional exposure of his infertile status, and it is captured thus:

I've never been sure if Funmi whispered those words or shouted them. But that night, it sounded as though the words were being bellowed; it felt as though they were echoing through every room in the house. She'd already let go of my trousers when I turned around to cover her mouth with my hand (260-261).

That patriarchy is idolised correlates with the findings of Pilcher, as cited in Peddie and Porter, that discussion on male infertility is unconventional in African societies (314). Rather, women are blamed when there is infertility in a marriage. This justifies why Moomi, Akin's mother, is let loose on Yejide, accusing her of being responsible for their childlessness. Moomi tells Yejide:

'Flat as the side of a wall,' ... 'you have had my son between your legs for two more months and still your stomach is flat. Close your thighs to him, I beg you. We all know how he feels about you. If you don't chase him away, he won't touch Funmi. If you don't, he will die childless. I beg you, don't spoil my life. He is my first son, Yejide (54).

Surprisingly, she does not inquire or investigate from his son about his reproductive health. She assumes that the cause must be his wife, Yejide. Significantly, Yejide finally confronts Akin about his impotency. Surprisingly, he still displays his masculine tendency by evading the answer; thus, he responds with questions instead of telling her the truth about his reproductive health. He believes that a man ought not to expose such weakness to a woman. This action clearly resonates with the cultural construction of masculinity in Africa, that men's impotency is not voiced.

Patriarchal Implications in Infertility

Adebayo decries the devastating implications of both the conscious and unconscious tendencies of patriarchy in issues of infertility. Akin's effort to prove himself a man by concealing his reproductive disease results in his wife giving birth to three children affected by sickle cell disease; two died. Not only that, his second son has to undergo frequent hospital admissions with excruciating pain. Yejide says of it:

I refused to entertain the possibility that he would die. I did not give up on Sesan; I held

on to him in my heart. I convinced myself that he would survive it all – the pain that made him scream until he was hoarse, the injections and painkillers being pumped into his body. I did not once wish that death would release him from his suffering. My only prayers were that he would survive it all and live (204).

Regrettably, Yejide suffers emotional oppression from her husband, who uses derogatory words on her. Additionally, after Akin's family and Yejide's to bring a second wife for him, and being informed of the plan, Akin chooses not to disclose it to Yejide; such an attitude is a manifestation of emotional oppression and relegation. It further reflects that the views and feelings of women are inconsequential. This follows that the male gender is superior to the female gender and, as such, dominates. Consequently, feminism denounces such disproportionate treatment of women. Further, Yejide is oppressed and subjugated by Baba Lola, who accuses her of being responsible for the couple's childlessness. He believes that the cause lies with Yejide, and assures her of good luck with the coming of the new wife: He says:

Well, our wife, this is your new wife. It is one child that calls another one into this world. Who knows, the king in heaven may answer your prayers because of this wife. Once she gets pregnant and has a child, we are sure you will have one too (16).

Baba Lola's words reflect the worldview of his society. He uses the expression, "your prayers" to suggest that Yejide is responsible for the alleged infertility. This creates a clear picture of a patriarchal society where men rarely come into view in infertility issues, rather women are labelled culprits. Men are projected as virile and fertile. Markedly, feminism castigates such ill treatment.

Consequently, Akin's evil tendencies and their exhibitions rob him of his marriage as Yejide finally deserts him. Subsequently, his health is neither probed nor considered as an inhibitor to the couple's fertility. This operation empowers Akin to demonstrate diverse masculine and patriarchal practices that adversely wrecked his wife and marriage. Feminism counters the oppression of women by men and seeks revolution against the objects of oppression or domination. Evidently, Yejide is unable to bear the evil meted out on her by Akin and leaves her marriage. Feminism lends a voice to women; it refines and enlightens. Her bold decision shows refinement as well as enlightenment. It is characteristic of radical feminism,

which employs force against women's oppression. This signifies revolution, which is an extreme approach to combat oppression against women.

Conclusion

This study reflects on the socio-cultural dynamics and impact of patriarchal African society on gender and family life. As advanced in the work, men symbolised by Akin have implicit tendencies that manifest in issues of male infertility with devastating consequences. These are fuelled by African cultures and norms, which are equally instruments of enforcing patriarchal and masculine ideologies. While men are rarely queried or blamed, the study reveals that women are blamed for issues of infertility and are recipients of resulting oppressions. Yejide's case stands out as a graphic portrayal of the plight of women in Africa. More so, African orientations present a picture of a perfect man who should be idolized. African norms tend to uphold that the impotency of a man is never voiced, as it is like emasculation. Adebayo decries and points at their devastating consequences. This study concludes that despite supposed global gains and progress in tackling forms of inequality, abuse, discrimination, and violence against women, glaring expressions and cases of patriarchy persist in Africa even beyond traditional settings.

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